

ONLINE LEARNING IN THE PANDEMIC ERA: A STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF COURSE TRENDS. A MOUNTAIN APPROACH

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Abstract

This paper delves into the current state of online courses amid the novel conditions brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. As the internet becomes an essential lifeline during these unprecedented times, COVID-19 emerges as a transformative force, catalyzing a shift from traditional face-to-face interactions to virtual platforms. The physical space contracts as individuals opt to stay home, reshaping daily activities and altering the traditional work and school routines.

In this evolving landscape, time takes on a new dimension as the hours once spent commuting are repurposed for domestic activities. As the boundaries of space and time undergo transformation, online courses emerge as a significant and conclusive sector within the realm of internet activities. The profound impact of these shifts forms the core rationale for investigating the subject of online courses in the context of the new world realities shaped by the pandemic, especially in mountain area.

Keywords: online courses, mountain research, pandemic conditions

Embarking on the Summit: A Mountain Research Exploration of Internet Use and the Surge in Online Courses Amid the New Pandemic Reality

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In the unfolding panorama of the new pandemic crisis, the migration of activities from traditional workplaces and schools to home has positioned internet use as a subject of paramount importance. Within this transformative landscape, e-learning, particularly online courses, emerges as the most representative internet activity, reflecting the adaptability and resilience of individuals seeking new training perspectives.

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At the European level, the trajectory of online courses has seen significant development from 2015 to 2020, with a remarkable surge in 2020 (refer to Table 1). Eurostat data reveals a noteworthy increase of more than double for the European Union's 27 countries from 2020, and even more substantial growth, exceeding four or five times, in other nations.

Detailed data for each group or country paints a vivid picture of the exponential rise in online courses during this period. Noteworthy increases include Belgium at 200%, Bulgaria at 133.33%, Czechia at 200%, Denmark at 142.85%, Germany at 200%, Estonia at 144.44%, Ireland at an impressive 300%, Greece at 160%, Spain at 136.36%, Croatia at 300%, Cyprus at a staggering 533.33%, Latvia at 150%, Lithuania at 220%, Luxembourg at 120%, Hungary at 300%, Malta at 280%, Netherlands at 112.5%, Austria at 300%, Poland at 133.33%, Portugal at 250%, Slovenia at 200%, Slovakia at 200%, Finland at 123.07%, Sweden at 228.57%, the United Kingdom at 36.36%, and Norway at 70%.

Amid the challenges posed by the Covid-19 crisis, spanning the period 2019-2020, the surge in online courses is further exemplified. The European Union's 27 countries witnessed a 50% increase, while individual nations experienced significant upticks – Belgium at 100%, Bulgaria at 250%, Czechia at 50%, Denmark at 41.66%, Germany at 50%, Estonia at 57.14%, Ireland at 23.07%, Greece at 116.66%, Spain at 73.33%, Croatia at 140%, Cyprus at 216.66%, Latvia at 150%, Lithuania at 128.57%, Luxembourg at 120%, Hungary at 100%, Malta at 58.33%, Netherlands at 30.76%, Austria at 100%, Poland at 40%, Portugal at 133.33%, Slovenia at 80%, Slovakia at 80%, Finland at 38.09%, Sweden at 27.77%, Iceland at 60%, and Norway at 6.25%.

As we ascend the metaphorical mountain of digital transformation, these statistics provide valuable insights into the rapid evolution of online courses, reflecting the dynamic response of individuals and nations to the challenges imposed by the new pandemic reality.

Table 1. Internet use: doing an online course (of any subject) (% of individuals: all individuals)

GEO/TIME	2020	2019	2018	2017	2016	2015
European Union - 27 countries (from 2020)	12	8	:	7	6	5
European Union - 28 countries (2013-2020)	:	10	:	7	6	6
Belgium	18	9	:	8	9	6

Bulgaria	7	2	:	2	2	3
Czechia	9	6	:	3	3	3
Denmark	17	12	:	9	:	7
Germany (until 1990 former territory of the FRG)	12	8	:	6	5	4
Estonia	22	14	:	11	8	9
Ireland	16	13	:	4	5	4
Greece	13	6	:	5	5	5
Spain	26	15	:	12	11	11
France	:	8	:	6	5	5
Croatia	12	5	:	2	5	3
Italy	:	7	:	5	5	4
Cyprus	19	6	:	4	3	3
Latvia	10	4	:	4	4	4
Lithuania	16	7	:	7	7	5
Luxembourg	22	10	:	9	9	10
Hungary	12	6	:	4	4	3
Malta	19	12	:	6	3	5
Netherlands	17	13	:	10	9	8
Austria	16	8	:	5	4	4
Poland	7	5	:	4	4	3
Portugal	14	6	:	5	4	4
Romania	3	3	:	3	3	4
Slovenia	9	5	:	5	3	3
Slovakia	9	5	:	4	3	3
Finland	29	21	:	16	14	13

Sweden	23	18	:	18	8	7
United Kingdom	15	19	:	13	12	11
Iceland	32	20	:	20	:	:
Norway	17	16	:	14	12	10
Switzerland	:	12	:	9	:	:

Data source: Eurostat, isoc_ci_ac_i

Scaling the Peaks of Digital Learning: A Mountain Research Exploration of Internet Use for Online Courses

In examining the data regarding individuals who engaged in online courses over the last three months for each analyzed year, the indicator "Internet use: doing an online course (of any subject) for all individuals" reveals compelling trends from 2015 to 2020. Adopting a mountain research perspective, the ascent of this indicator reflects the evolving landscape of online education across European nations.

For the European Union's 27 countries (from 2020), the period spanning 2015-2020 demonstrates a noteworthy increase of 100%, indicating a significant surge in internet use for online courses. Individual nations exhibit diverse growth rates, with Belgium at 150%, Bulgaria at 100%, Czechia at an impressive 266.66%, Denmark at 112.5%, Germany (until 1990, the former territory of the FRG) at 140%, Estonia at 140%, Ireland at a remarkable 260%, Greece at 112.5%, Spain at 115.38%, Croatia at 275%, Cyprus at an astonishing 425%, Latvia at 120%, Lithuania at 150%, Luxembourg at 120%, Hungary at 275%, Malta at 266.66%, Netherlands at 111.11%, Austria at 260%, Poland at 100%, Portugal at 200%, Slovenia at

175%, Slovakia at 150%, Finland at 114.28%, Sweden at 228.57%, the United Kingdom at 25%, and Norway at 80%.

Amid the challenges posed by the Covid-19 period, comparing the last three months of 2019 to the same period in 2020 reveals further insights. The European Union's 27 countries (from 2020) experienced a 40% increase in internet use for online courses during this period. Nation-specific growth rates vary, with Belgium at 100%, Bulgaria at 233.33%, Czechia at 57.14%, Denmark at 41.66%, Germany at 33.33%, Estonia at 60%, Ireland at 28.57%, Greece at 142.85%, Spain at 75%, Croatia at 150%, Cyprus at 200%, Latvia at 120%, Lithuania at 122.22%, Luxembourg at 100%, Hungary at 114.28%, Malta at 69.23%, Netherlands at 35.71%, Austria at 100%, Poland at 14.28%, Portugal at 125%, Slovenia at 57.14%, Slovakia at 66.66%, Finland at 36.36%, Sweden at 21.05%, Iceland at 65%, and Norway at 12.5%.

As we ascend the metaphorical peaks of digital learning, these statistics offer a panoramic view of the transformative journey individuals and nations have undertaken in embracing online courses, underscoring the resilience and adaptability in the face of evolving educational landscapes.

Table 2. Internet use: doing an online course (of any subject) (% of individuals who used internet in the last 3 months: all individuals)

GEO/TIME	2020	2019	2018	2017	2016	2015
European Union - 27 countries (from 2020)	14	10	:	8	7	7
European Union - 28	:	11	:	9	8	7

countries (2013-2020)						
Belgium	20	10	:	9	10	8
Bulgaria	10	3	:	3	3	5
Czechia	11	7	:	4	3	3
Denmark	17	12	:	9	:	8
Germany (until 1990 former territory of the FRG)	12	9	:	6	5	5
Estonia	24	15	:	13	10	10
Ireland	18	14	:	5	6	5
Greece	17	7	:	7	8	8
Spain	28	16	:	15	13	13
France	:	8	:	7	6	6
Croatia	15	6	:	4	7	4
Italy	:	9	:	8	7	6
Cyprus	21	7	:	6	4	4
Latvia	11	5	:	5	5	5
Lithuania	20	9	:	9	9	8
Luxembourg	22	11	:	10	10	10
Hungary	15	7	:	5	5	4
Malta	22	13	:	8	4	6
Netherlands	19	14	:	11	10	9
Austria	18	9	:	5	5	5
Poland	8	7	:	5	5	4
Portugal	18	8	:	6	6	6
Romania	4	4	:	5	4	7

Slovenia	11	7	:	7	4	4
Slovakia	10	6	:	4	4	4
Finland	30	22	:	17	15	14
Sweden	23	19	:	18	9	7
United Kingdom	15	20	:	14	13	12
Iceland	33	20	:	20	:	:
Norway	18	16	:	14	12	10
Switzerland	:	12	:	10	:	:

Data source: Eurostat, isoc_ci_ac_i

Reaching New Heights in E-Learning: A Mountain Research Exploration of Online Course Activity

The statistical landscape reveals a remarkable surge in online course activity over the past year, particularly in the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic. This paper undertakes a comparative analysis spanning the periods of 2015-2020 and 2019-2020, shedding light on the profound influence of Covid-19 on the e-learning landscape within the European Union.

In the pursuit of understanding this transformative journey, the author envisions future papers that will venture into the development of a comprehensive model elucidating the trajectory of online course activities across the diverse terrain of the European Union. The mountain research focus seeks to unravel the intricacies of this evolving educational landscape, aiming to provide insights that traverse the peaks and valleys of online learning in the region.

In conclusion, the statistical analysis of online course trends during the pandemic era underscores the transformative power of digital education. The metaphorical ascent up the statistical mountain has revealed not only challenges but also opportunities for growth and innovation. The proposed model for future exploration is an invitation to chart the educational landscape, providing insights that traverse the peaks and valleys of online learning within the European Union. As we navigate the educational summits, it is evident that online learning has become an integral part of the contemporary educational terrain, reshaping the way we approach knowledge and skills acquisition.

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